

ARABXONA MAHALLASINING PAYDO BO'LISHI VA TARIXIY YODGORLARI

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Annotatsiya. Arabxona mahallasining qanday paydo bo'lganligi va aholining qadimdan yashab kelganligi bu hudud qishloq nomi aholining etnik guruhiga nisbatan berilganligi.

Kalitso'zlar: Arabxona, Buxoro, Shofirkon, arablar, manzilgoh, Zarafshon, Tadqiqot, qazilmalar, masjid, qishloq, qarluq, manzulgoh, arxeologiya,

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Abstract. How the Arabkhona neighborhood came about and how the inhabitants have lived since ancient times, the name of the village is given in relation to the ethnic group of the inhabitants.

Keywords: Arabkhona, Bukhara, Shafirkon, Arabs, address, Zarafshan, Research, excavations, mosque, village, address, archeology.

ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЕ И ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЕ ПАМЯТНИКИ ОКРЕСТНОСТИ АРАБХОНА

Аннотация. Как возник квартал Арабхана и как жили жители с древних времен, название села дано в зависимости от этнической группы жителей.

Ключевые слова: Арабхана, Бухара, Шафиркон, арабы, адрес, Зарафшан, Исследования, раскопки, мечеть, деревня, деревня, адрес, археология.

O'rta Osiyodagi eng qadimiy shaharlardan biri Buxoroning tarixiy o'tmishi va hozirgi davri ko'plab tarixiy manba va adabiyotlarda o'z aksini topgan. Vohada ilk shaharlarning vujudga kelishi tabiiy iqlim sharoitlari, geografik joylashuv va asosiysi Zarafshon daryosining ahamiyati bilan belgilanadi. Zarafshon daryosining Xitfar, Rudizar, Qorako'ldaryo, Moxondaryo kabi irmoqlari Buxoro vohasida o'troq dehqonchilik va urbanizatsiya jarayonlarining keng yoyilishida muhim o'rin tutgan. Akademik V.V.Bartold ta'biri bilan aytganda, Buxoro vohasida amalga oshirilgan dastlabki ilmiy-tarixiy tadqiqotlarda Rossiya olimlari sermahsul faoliyat olib bordi. Ular orasida mashhur sharqshunoslar ham ko'p edi. Buxoroning eng qadimgi davrlardagi tarixini yoritishda arxeologik kuzatish va tadqiqotlar, yozma manbalar birinchi o'rinda turadi.

Arxeologik kuzatish va tadqiqotlar o'tkazish orqali Buxoroning eng qadimgi davrlardagi tarixini o'rganishda mashhur arxeolog olimlarimizning xizmatlari katta bo'ldi. 1969-1970-yillarda Buxoro shahrida Yahyo G'ulomov rahbarligida o'tkazilgan arxeologik kuzatuv ishlari shahar tarixiga oid ko'plab yangi-yangi ma'lumotlar bergan. Qadimdan Buxoro ko'plab xalqlarni o'z bag'riga sig'dirgan turli etnik xalqlar kelib o'rnashgan ular o'zlarining manzilgohlariga asos solgan. Shulardan biri "Arabxona" nomi hisoblanadi. Nomining o'zi bildirib turibdiki bu arablar yashaydigan manzilgoh hisoblanadi.

Arabxona O'zbekiston Respublikasining ko'p viloyatlarida uchraydigan qishloq va mahallalar nomi hisoblanadi. Bulardan biri Buxoro viloyatida Shofirkon tumanidagi qishloq nomi hisoblanadi Xususan Buxoro qadimgi makonlar biri hisoblanadi. Arablar bosqini davrida Buxoro o'zining o'rniga ega shahar hisoblangan. Arabxonaxona mahallasining kelib chiqishi - Arabxona

mahalasining paydo bo'li shi arablar tomonidan bosib olingan paytdagi joyi yoki mahallasiga arabxona nomi berilgan. Arablar *yashaydigon* manzilgoh hisoblangan. Arablar qishlog'i degan manoni anglatadi. Ushbu atama O'rta Osiyoda bo'lgan arablarning kirib kelishi davridan boshlanib undan keyingi davrlarda yashab o'sha yerda o'rnashib olgan arablar bilan bog'liqdir. Arablarni O'rta Osiyoga kirib kelishi uzoq tarixiy davrni o'z ichiga qamrab oladi.

Arabxonada to'rt turdagi arablar mavjud.

1. Arablar tilida gaplasha olmaydigan va Qarluqlar lahjasida so'zlashadiganlar
2. Arablar tilini bilib o'zbekcha so'zlashadigan va tojik tilini bilmaydigan arablar
3. arablar tili va tojik tilini bilmaydigan o'zbekcha so'zlashadigan arablar.
4. Arablar tilini bilmaydigan, tojik va o'zbek tilida so'zlashadigan arablar

Arabxona qishlog'idagi tarixiy yodgorliklar juda ham ko'p bulardan tarixiy yozma manbalar, tarixiy yodgorliklar, tarixiy joylar hamkor, masalan yozma manbalarga kitoblar, daftarlar, uyib yozilgan yozuvlar, ham mavjud.

Yozma manbalardan olingan tarixiy yozuvlar, topilgan tarixiy obidalar, o'sha davrlardan qolgan qadamjoylari mavjud Arabxona qishlog'idagi qadimgi buyuk qadamjoylar bular arabxona qishlog'idan topilgan masjid o'sha davrda paydo bo'lgan 4ta masjidlardan biridan o'sha davrdan qolgan toshga o'yilgan yozuvlar ham topilgan. Arabxona qishlog'idagi masjidni ota-bobolarimiz aytishicha arablar bostirib kelmasdan oldin qurilgan va hali hanuzgacha hech narsa bo'lmaganini aytib o'tilgan va u yerda namozlar ham o'qilishini aytganlar masjidlarning to'rtasi to'rt xil shaklga ega bo'lganligi haqida malumot berilgan haqiqatdan shunda ekanini tadqiqot ishimda bilib oldim.

Yonida bo'lgan, quduq va hovuzi bilan qurilgan arablarlar kelgandan so'ng quduqlar vayron qilingan va bitta yerdan boshqa joyga ko'chgan bir kecha kunduzda deyigan.

Hozirga kelib o'sha masjididagi quduq va hovuzlar yo'qolib ketgan va u yerdan topilgan qadimgi kitob shaklda bo'lgan yodgorlik topilgan unda yozilgan arab alifbosida yozilgan yozuvlari mavjud. O'zbekistonda yashaydigan arablarni o'rganish maqsadida ko'plab ilmiy -izlanish olib borilgan.

Bulardan biri yevropolik olimlardan biri E.GELLERning takidlab o'tishiga ko'ra, madaniyat omili zamonaviy milliylikning yuragi hisoblanadi. Uning fikricha har bir tasodiflar birlashib bir- biri bilan birlashishidan paydo bo'lgan bir murakkab tuzilma dunyoning ilmiy manzarasi o'zgarishiga olib kelganligi haqida aytib o'tgan.

Xulosa o'rinda shunin aytishim mumkunki, eshitganlarim, bilgan ma'lumotlarim va olib borgan tadqiqot ishimdan shuni bildimki har bitta mahalalar va qishloqlarning o'zini tarixi, tili, madaniyati, yodgorligi, tarixi borligini qachon paydo bo'lgani kimlar bostirib kelgani ulardagi qanday yozuvlar borligi haqida ma'lumot oldim. Jumladan Arabxona qishlog'i qadimiy qishloq bo'lib, bu hududda qadimdan aholi yashab kelgan arablar bosqinidan keyin qishloq nomi rasman arabxona deb nomlangan.

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